

ANALYSIS OF THE HYDROLOGICAL REGIME AND MORPHOMETRIC
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MEZHDURECHENSKOYE RESERVOIR

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Abstract. The article examines the current hydrological state of the Amudarya delta lake systems amid the Aral Sea desiccation. The lakes are categorized into three feeding zones: Left Bank, Priamudarya, and Right Bank. Particular focus is placed on the Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir as the key regulatory facility. The study provides its primary morphometric characteristics, analyzing the dynamics of water area and volume fluctuations. The findings emphasize the potential of the Priamudarya zone for ecological and economic restoration through effective freshwater management.

Keywords: Amudarya delta, Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir, hydrology, morphometry, water resources, South Priaralie.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada Orol dengizi qurishi sharoitida Amudaryo deltasi ko'llarining gidrologik holati tahlil qilingan. Ko'llar oziqlanish manbalariga ko'ra uchta zonaga ajratib o'rganilgan. Asosiy e'tibor suv taqsimotini tartibga soluvchi Mejdurechie suv omborining morfometrik tavsiflari va suv hajmi dinamikasiga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari daryo bo'yi zonasi ko'llarini chuchuk suv bilan ta'minlash orqali mintaqa iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlarini ko'rsatib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Amudaryo deltasi, Mejdurechie suv ombori, gidrologiya, morfometriya, suv resurslari, Janubiy Orolbo'yi.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается современное гидрологическое состояние озёрных систем дельты Амударьи в условиях высыхания Аральского моря. Озера классифицированы по трём зонам питания. Основное внимание уделено Междуреченскому водохранилищу как ключевому регулируемому объекту. Представлены его основные морфометрические характеристики, проанализирована динамика изменения площади и объёма воды. Сделаны выводы о возможностях экологического восстановления Приамударьинской зоны при эффективном управлении ресурсами.

Ключевые слова: дельта Амударьи, Междуреченское водохранилище, гидрология, морфометрия, водные ресурсы, Южное Приаралье.

As of 1965, the total area of the delta was 8990 km² (Rogov M.M., 1965). At that time, separate lake systems such as the Muynak, Rybachy (Sarybas) gulfs, Dumalak, Zhilyrbas, and Sudochie were united with the Aral Sea and had communication with each other. In the following years, due to the lowering of the Aral Sea level, the process of draining the shallow part of the sea started; water in the Adjibay Bay and Zhilyrbas Bay completely disappeared; at the same time, water was leaving Muynak and Rybachiy Bays.

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Taking into account the existing circumstances, in 1975-80, it was necessary to develop a project on creation of artificially regulated reservoirs in the delta in order to retain river water in the former sea bays Muynak, Rybachi, Zhilyrbas, Mezhdurechiye (Shegekul), Mahpalkul, and a number of other small bays. This project envisaged construction of barrier dams from the seaside, irrigation canals, and the beginning of water accumulation in these reservoirs. This was the only correct solution in this situation, when the sea level was irrevocably decreasing, and it was losing its national systems have changed greatly during the last 30-35 years. For example, in the high-water year of 1992, when 24.1 km³ of river runoff entered the delta, the area of delta lakes was filled completely and reached up to 369.0 - 425.0 thousand hectares (according to space images). During low-water years, such as 2000-2002, the area of these lakes decreased to 5.0 thousand ha.

The main water body of national economic importance is the Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir; it is the first water body downstream of the Takhiatash hydroscheme that receives river flow, and the operation regime of other water bodies depends on it. The reservoir is located between the Akdarya and Kipchakdarya river channels. The total area of the reservoir at its full filling is 49.0 thousand ha (according to space images of 1992). Research works on the study of the Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir was not carried out to the full extent, and in the light of frequent water deficit observed in recent years in our region, especially in our republic, it is urgent to study this reservoir. One of the components of scientific research is the determination of the water regime and morphometric characteristics of water bodies in the Amudarya Iver delta.

Current state of water management facilities. Before 1963-64 all lakes mainly existed at the expense of Amu Darya river water (except for some lakes, which were fed by sea water inflow) and water in them was fresh and quite suitable for fish and muskrat breeding, also favourable conditions for reed and other aquatic vegetation growth were created. Mineralisation of water of these lakes was low and ranged from 0.334 to 1.20 g/l in dense residue.

Subsequently, as the level of the Aral Sea decreased, the sea bays and coastal inland delta lakes began to dry up. In 1975-80, Lakes Dumalak, Dzhanylysh, Shege, Koksu, Zakirkul, and Uzynaydyn almost dried up. The areas of lakes Mashankul, Dautkul and a number of others have significantly reduced.

Due to the construction of main drainage routes (since 1963), drainage-discharge water started to flow into Sudochie, Karateren, Akchakul and a number of other small lakes. At present such lakes as Sudochie, Karateren mainly exist due to inflow of collector waters. Usually, the waters of these collectors are moderately and strongly mineralised, with a lot of various salts, pesticides, organochlorine compounds in their composition, in connection with which they are considered unpromising for their use for fishery purposes. In 1983-84, filling of lakes at the

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seaside and intra-delta lakes (Mezhdurechye, Dumalak) mainly along the Amudarya River started.

Taking into account the current situation, in 1975-1980 SANIIRI (now Research Institute of Irrigation and Water Problems) developed a variant of developing a system of shallow reservoirs on the dried seabed (V.A.Dukhovny and others) to retain river water in the former sea bays.

At present, they can be divided into 3 types according to their feeding regime:

- a) lakes fed by Amu Darya water;
- b) lakes fed by collector water;
- c) lakes fed by mixed water.

According to the nature of water availability and quality of water used, the Amudarya river delta territory can be divided into 3 zones:

1. Left bank zone is a system of lakes Sudochie, Karateren, Mashankul, etc., which are fed by collector water.
2. Priamudarya zone - these are seaside intra-delta lakes fed from the river.
3. Right-bank zone - these are lakes Zhiltirbas, Karateren, which are fed by mixed water.

Table 1 shows the main characteristics of water bodies located in the Amudarya River delta.

Table 1
Main characteristics of water bodies located in the Amudarya river delta at the present level

Name of lakes and water reservoirs	Area, thous. ha	Required volume of water intake, mln m ³	Mark, m	
			H _{max.}	H _{min.}
Mezhdurechye	32,0	252,0	57,4	54,0
Rybachie	6,4	104,0	52,2	49,6
Muynak	9,75	163,0	51,7	49,6
Sudoche	44,0	650,0	52,7	52,1
Karateren	18,0	234	52,0	52,4
Karazhar	34,0	442	52,4	52,2
Zhiltirbas	28,5	477	52,1	49,2

The first left-bank zone is unfavourable in terms of its quality and productivity due to constant supply of collector water. In the future, due to reduction of the Amudarya River water availability downstream of the Takhiatash hydroscheme, fresh water supply and volume of collector runoff will be reduced and their salinity will increase accordingly. The main objective of this zone is to preserve Sudochie Lake as a natural object and the chain of Karateren lake systems.

The most promising of these zones is the second Priamudarya zone. If guaranteed flow is released through the Takhiatash hydroscheme, favourable ecological, hydrological and hydrochemical conditions will be created along the whole length of the river channel from Samanbay gauging station to the Aral Sea.

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The third zone is the right-bank zone, where the majority of water bodies are also fed by collector waters KS-1, KS-3, and partly river water enters this zone through the Kazakhdarya channel from the Amudarya River to Lake Zhiltirbas.

The solution of the issue of preservation of these lakes, improvement of ecological situation and increase of productivity in this zone depends on water availability and its quality, mainly on the volume of Amudarya water. In high-water years, as a result of large volumes of river water entering the Amudarya delta through the river channel and tailings of irrigation canals, the condition of these lakes has significantly improved (especially in the Priamudarya zone) and even led to an increase in their areas.

a) Left-bank zone. This is a large massif covering the left-bank part of the Amudarya River, territory of Kungrad and Muynak districts. The source of lakes feeding in this zone is the tail part of the Suenli canal and the KKS collector with its inlets. Such lakes as Sudochie, Karateren and a number of other small lakes are located in this zone. Due to sharp reduction of water inflow from the river through the Raushan channel, such numerous lakes as Altynkul, Mashankul, Khozhakul and a number of others have dried up. The largest area is occupied by Lake Sudochie, which in high-water years mainly exists on the basis of collector runoff and partly river water. Water is poured into the depressions of the eastern part of the lake towards the Karadjar lake system. Due to changes in the volume of water inflow from the river on the side of the Ustyurt collector and from the KKS, there are multi-year and seasonal changes in the horizon and, accordingly, in the areas of the water mirror in this system of lakes.

In low-water years, the areas of these lakes are reduced by 2 and 3 times, and at the same time water quality deteriorates. In years of average water availability and in low-water years, river water inflow to these lakes stops completely. Analysis of long-term data on changes in water quality and the state of vegetation and other biological resources shows that long-term watering with collector water, especially in recent years, has led to a sharp increase in water salinity and a decrease in the productivity of these lakes.

b) Priamudarya zone. This zone covers the vast territory of the delta from the Takhiatash hydrosystem to the Aral Sea. In this zone there are freshwater lakes such as Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir, Dumalak, Muynak and Rybachie bays and a number of other small lakes, which are mainly fed from the Amu Darya River and its channels. Such lakes as Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir, Rybachie and Muynak Bays are artificially regulated water bodies that have been created in recent years in place of dried up littoral and inland lakes and sea bays. At present, these lakes are in relatively good condition in terms of water quality and in hydrological-hydrochemical and ecological terms. Especially it is felt in the littoral part of the lakes as on Dumalak, Rybachiy and Muynak bays. In recent years, when water enters

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the bowls of these lakes, reeds appear, fish catch increases and the ecological situation in this zone improves significantly.

All these lakes have a great prospect as they are fed mainly by Amu Darya river water, favourable water-salt regime is created here, they have a great prospect for fish breeding, muskrat breeding and creation of fodder production base for cattle breeding.

Water regime regulation issues of all lakes located in this zone, in particular Rybachie and Muynak bays mainly depend on operation regime of the shallow Mezhdurechensk reservoir. The shallow part of this reservoir makes it extremely difficult to solve the issue of both release of maximum water flow through the Amudarya river channel to the sea and guaranteed water supply to all other lakes and reservoirs. The production of fish farming, muskrat breeding and cattle breeding in the delta is based on these lakes located in the Priamudarya zone. The development of the national economy and employment of the population of Muynak district fully depend on the productivity of these reservoirs.

Right-bank zone. The considered zone is located on the right side of the Amu Darya River and occupies a huge area of irrigated lands of the Kyzketken canal system. The largest lakes, Lake Karateren and Lake Zhiltirbas, exist mainly due to collector discharge formed from the irrigated lands. Such small lakes as Atakul, Maukul and a number of others dry up completely in dry years.

In general, it can be noted that in such lakes as Sudochie, Zhiltirbas, Karateren (western and eastern) and a number of small lakes, which are fed by collector water, the hydrochemical and hydrobiological state of water deteriorates, their mineralisation increases and, accordingly, these lakes gradually lose their national economic significance. Every year the areas of saline soils increase, reed habitats decrease and turn into solonchak depression. As for the Priamudarya zone, further development of the situation here depends on the volume of fresh water supplied from the Amudarya River.

Current status of water management facilities in the Amudarya River delta. Due to the lowering of the Aral Sea level and the draining of the sea bays, huge changes took place in the Amu Darya delta. Starting from 1968-1970, the Adjibay, Muynak, Rybachy and Zhiltirbas bays were drained. Taking this into account, design and survey works on creation of artificial reservoirs on the territory of former sea bays were started. Blocking dams, outlet and overflow hydraulic structures were built, resulting in the creation of artificial lakes Muynak, Rybachie, Mezhdurechenskoye, Zhiltirbas, Sudochie and a number of other small lakes.

Large water management construction works have been carried out in the Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir. Due to this, water management and distribution capacities in the delta have now been created. Despite this, guaranteed and safe water management has not yet been achieved. There is a particular danger in the operation of these structures in high-water years.

2.1 Status of water management facilities in the Priamudarya zone

This is a large array of lake systems fed by fresh Amu Darya water. These freshwater lakes are the main water bodies, and if water is available, they can be considered promising for fish, muskrat breeding and livestock development. Most importantly, there are large freshwater lakes such as Mezhdurechye, Muynak and Rybachiy bays, Dumalak system of lakes and a number of other small lakes that have ecological, socio-economic and national economic importance in the Amudarya delta.

The Priamudarya zone includes the following water management facilities: Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir covering a complex of hydraulic structures and canal system, Muynak, Rybachie bays, Dumalak lake system and Kungrad-Muynak canal.

Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir. Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir is the first reservoir that receives river flow and therefore, on the one hand, it is considered an important object and the regime of other reservoirs depends on it, but on the other hand, it is the most difficult to operate object, where one can constantly expect a critical situation during the passage of maximum water flows along the river.

Muynak Bay. The source of the lake's water supply is the Glavmyaso canal, which originates from the Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir.

The maximum depth reaches up to 3.5 metres, but the water depth in most areas is 0.5-0.7 metres. Enclosing dams and temporary catchment structures have been constructed on the western side. Water mineralisation has been increasing in recent years (especially in low-water years) and reaches up to 3.5-4.0 g/l, while in high-water years it decreases to 2.5-3.0 g/l.

Rybachy Bay. The reservoir was built on the site of the dried up Sarybas Bay in 1974, which was connected to the Aral Sea. By means of enclosing dams from the north and west and a water outlet structure, river water was accumulated in the bowl of the reservoir. The maximum depth reaches up to 3.5-4.0 m, the prevailing depth is 0.8-1.5 m. The mineralisation of the reservoir water varies from 1.5 to 3.0 g/l depending on the fresh water input. The total replenishment of the lake by 50-55% has favourable conditions for reproduction of fish and muskrat. In low-water years the area of the lake sharply decreases.

Status of water management facilities in the Left Bank Zone. Lake Sudochie. Lake Sudochie consists of 4 small reservoirs like Agushpa, Begdulla-aidyn, Bolshoye Sudochie, Karateren, which are connected to each other by natural and artificial channels. Before the reconstruction of the lake (1999-2004), the lake was fed mainly through the collectors of the KKS, GK and fresh water from the tail part of the Suenli canal. The Lake Sudochie system includes the following water bodies: Lake Agushpa, Lake Begdulla-aidyn, Lake Bolshoye Sudochie, Lake Karateren, the end part of the KKS collector, the Sudochie canal, the 17 km long Akkum dam, and an outlet structure on the Akkum dam designed for 55 m³/sec.

2.2 Status of water management facilities in the Right Bank Zone

The zone under consideration covers the right-bank part of the Amu Darya River. Lakes Zhiltirbas and Karateren are located on its territory. Feeding canals, dams and hydraulic structures have been built on these water bodies.

Lake Zhiltirbas. The water body was created on the dried bottom of the Aral Sea. The bay is mainly formed due to the discharge of collector-drainage water from collectors KS-1, KS-3 and periodically due to flood discharges of river water through the Kazakhdarya channel. To maintain the water level on the north-eastern side, the embankment dam is embanked. The crest elevation of the dam is 52.0 metres. The total length of the dam is 30.4 km. The condition of the dam is satisfactory. Main collector KS-1.

Mezhdurechenskoye water reservoir. Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir is the first reservoir downstream of the Takhiatash hydroscheme that receives river runoff, and the operation regime of the other reservoirs depends on it. The reservoir is located between the Akdarya and Kipchakdarya river channels. The total area of the reservoir at its full filling is 49.0 thousand ha (according to space images of 1992). According to instrumental survey data of NGO ‘Eco Priaralie’ as of July 2002, the reservoir area was equal to 34.2 thousand ha.

When designing the complex of structures of the Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir, several options were developed to select types and designs of spillway structures, such as the Bortovoy spillway, spillway structures. Nevertheless, at present the total discharge capacity of the Mezhdurechenskoye reservoir at a horizon level of 56.8 m does not exceed 300 - 350 m³/s.

2.3 Main morphometric characteristics of the Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir

Depending on the water content of the year, the water surface area of the reservoir varies from 4.0 to 34.0 thousand ha. The morphological characteristics of the Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir were assessed using the results of a survey of the area and an isobath map, which was used to determine the corresponding areas and water volume for different horizons (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 - Plan of the Mezhdurechenskoye Reservoir in isobaths

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As can be seen from the data, at full filling of the reservoir the value of maximum water surface area is 34.0 thousand ha and water volume is 150.0 million m³ accordingly. At minimum horizons (50 - 52 m BS) water remains in the old channels of Akdarya and Kipchakdarya and in the channels formed as a result of dam breach. The deepest part of the reservoir is located in the central and north-western parts of the lake. The areas between the 56.0 and 57.0 m BS horizons belong to the periodically flooded zones. The maximum depth at full filling (57.0 - 57.30 m BS) is 5.5 - 6.0 m (according to the Amudarya river bed). In the shallow part between horizontals 55.30 - 57.0 the lake is overgrown with aquatic vegetation (mainly reeds), water depth does not exceed 1.0 - 1.5 metres.

Conclusion. At present we can definitely say that based on the expected hydrological and hydrochemical conditions, it is necessary to recognise the absolute futility of both the fishery and from the ecological point of view of the territory of the Left Bank and Right Bank zones in case the situation remains at the level of today. Due to the fact that these reservoirs are fed by highly mineralised collector water, further deterioration is expected in hydrological, hydrobiological and hydrochemical regimes and, accordingly, they will gradually lose their national economic significance.

Taking into account the real situation, it is possible to say more or less definitely that for quite a long time, even based on the assumption of further reduction of water availability downstream of the Takhiatash hydroscheme, the Amudarya River water will be sufficient for creation of freshwater regulated lake systems in the Central Priamudarya zone. This requires a set of measures in the zone of Mezhdurechye, Muynak and Rybachy gulfs. Most importantly, everything will depend, firstly, on what volume of water will be discharged downstream of the Takhiatash hydroscheme, and secondly, on how to use the available water resources.

At the same time, we cannot agree with the positions that have been held until today that excessive runoff should be discharged at any cost towards the Aral Sea; this has no real basis. On the contrary, when designing facilities, it is necessary to envisage all possible options for their retention in the nearest water bodies, so that this water could be used to increase the productivity of these water bodies (fish, muskrat, reeds, etc.) and thus at least partially restore the natural wealth of this region.

List of references:

1. Духовный В.А. и др. Южное Приаралье – новые перспективы. // Ташкент, 2003. - С. 29-52
2. Духовный В.А. Водная и экологическая стабильность в Центральной Азии // Проблемы Аральского моря и Приаралья. НИЦ МКВК, 2008. - С. 4-13.
3. Крейцберг-Мухина Е., Мирабдуллаев И., Тальских В. Основные результаты экологического мониторинга ветланда Судочье. // Экологическая устойчивость и передовые подходы к управлению водными ресурсами в бассейне Аральского моря. Алматы, 2003. - С. 355.

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4. Курбанбаев Е. Проблема Арала и Приаралья // Материалы Международного семинара «Экологические факторы и здоровье матери/ребенка в регионе Аральского кризиса», ФАН РУз. Ташкент, 2001. - С.34-42.
5. Курбанбаев Е., Каримова О.Ю., Курбанбаев С.Е. Оценка качества коллекторно-дренажных вод и возможность их повторного использования в низовьях реки Амударьи // Тезисы докладов Международной конференции «Мировой опыт и передовые технологии эффективного использования водных ресурсов». Ашхабад, 2010. – С. 268-271.
6. Курбанбаев Е., Артыков О., Курбанбаев С. Интегрированное управление водными ресурсами в дельте реки Амударьи // Ташкент, 2010. - 156 с.
7. Курбанбаев Е., Артыков О., Курбанбаев С. Аральское море и водохозяйственная политика в республиках Центральной Азии // Нукус, 2011. – 139 с.
8. Курбанбаев С.Е., Каримова О.Ю. Возможные варианты, обеспечивающие безопасную эксплуатацию Междуреченского водохранилища // Тезисы докладов III Международной научно-практической конференции «Проблемы рационального использования и охрана биологических ресурсов Южного Приаралья. Нукус. 2010. – С. 91-92.
9. Курбанбаев С.Е. Изменение гидрографической сети дельты реки Амударьи за период XIX-XX // Вестник ККО АН РУз. №1, Нукус, 2015. - С.14-19.
10. Курбанбаев С.Е. Изменение гидрографической сети дельты реки Амударьи в период снижения уровня Аральского моря // Вестник ККО АН РУз. №2. Нукус, 2015. - С.21-24.
11. Курбанбаев С., Каримова О., Т. Калимбетов., И.Каипов. Водный режим озер приаралья и основные морфометрические характеристики междуреченского водохранилища. //Central Asian Journal Of Theoretical And Applied Sciences//Volume: 04 Issue: 01 | Jan 2023 ISSN: 2660-5317 <https://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org>